

THE ROLE OF DIDACTIC TOOLS IN THE PROCESS OF FORMING CHILDREN'S SPEECH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Kamola Tursunbayeva

2nd stage graduate student, ADPI Pre-school education direction

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7810682>

Abstract. *Didactic games are a means of education for preschool children, help to successfully implement it, teach children the native language by forming expressive, clear, concise and figurative speech, teach children gives lim.*

Keyword: *first step, speech, method, time, word, scientific, methodology, didactic, legality, educator.*

The main task of preschool education is to prepare children for school education. That is, in preschool education, children are required not only to acquire specific knowledge, but also to acquire thinking skills, understand the speech of their peers and adults, freely exchange ideas with them, and work on the basis of cooperation. It is necessary for children to think imaginatively and logically in their native language, to express their ideas correctly through speech, to control themselves, to manage themselves, to have mental training such as observation, hearing, remembering, generalization, comparison. In fulfilling this task, the role and importance of the science of speaking in the mother tongue is great. Because language is a means of communication between people, it serves equally for all people, therefore language is a social phenomenon, changes and updates in the development of society are reflected in language.

Language units form speech, that is, each person expresses his thoughts to others through language, through language units, and understands the thoughts of others through language. That is, the speech is to convey the thoughts and discussions about the surrounding events to others. Therefore, language and speech are important in human life. In preschool education, teaching the science of the method of speech development, knowing the methods of speech development, allows to correctly solve the tasks of children's speech development in each age group, and ensures the fulfillment of the task of preparing children for school. From the above-mentioned points, it can be concluded that the Uzbek language has developed as an ancient language and is serving the members of the society at all stages of the development of the society.

The independence of our republic had a positive impact on the development of the Uzbek language, our language expresses the essence of independence and serves to improve mother tongue education at all stages of the educational system. Developing children's speech in preschool education means practical learning of their mother tongue.

The methodology of speech development as a pedagogical science developed in the structure of the pedagogical science until the 1920s, and then it was formed as an independent science.

The method of speech development as a pedagogical discipline, as a customer in the training of a specialist who has thoroughly mastered the development of children's speech in preschool education, introducing the base program "Ilk Kadam" created on the basis of scientific research into the educational process, knowledge of the speech development methodology and

ensures theoretical and practical proportionality of skills formation, develops methods of speech development. To improve it, to practically teach children their native language by using the most convenient method, to use language units in speech, to be able to correctly express thoughts in their native language in the context of mutual speech, to understand the speech of their peers by listening to it, and to be able to distinguish language units in speech (sound, word) forms the activity of learning and following the standards of speech in accordance with the work.

So, the science of speech development methodology fulfills the task of speech development in preschool education, by forming expressive, clear, clear and figurative speech in children, it practically teaches the mother tongue and educates children.

The science of the method of speech development is the development of children's oral speech in preschool education, the correct and appropriate use of words in speech, that is, the owner of speech and behavior by forming the skills of speech interaction with peers and adults forms the acquisition of moral and moral qualities, such as being. The methodology of speech development performs a developmental task as a pedagogical science. That is, by systematically developing children's speech, it ensures fluent intelligibility of speech through anatomical-gymnastic exercises of their speech organs: it develops children's thinking and mental activity, forms speech etiquette and moral perfection in them. Because well-developed speech is understandable and impressive, the child corrects his speech. The methodology of speech development as a pedagogical science studies the pedagogical laws of children's speech development, the formation and requirements of pedagogical activity, develops the most effective factors, means, methods and methods of speech development based on the achievements of modern pedagogy, scientific pedagogical requirements, recommends education, science. In addition, the importance of didactic games in the development of children's speech, the rules used in the didactic game were considered a criterion for determining the correctness or incorrectness of game actions and evaluating them. Learning the rules of the game and following them will help the child to develop independence, self-control and mutual control during the game.

Speech is very important in the game process. Through speech, children exchange ideas, share their feelings and experiences. Speech helps to establish friendly relations between children, to have a uniform attitude to the events of life around them. While the educator is leading the children's game, they also educate through the team. Thus, didactic games are a means of teaching children of preschool age, help to successfully implement it, and also help to bring children to school.

Developing speech: didactic games for children's speech development

1. To develop listening to speech (hearing different sounds and letters)

Your leader will call out the letter that you need to "catch" the word, for example, the sound "Sh". In turn, words with the presence of this letter and without it: school, class, student, cabinet, scarf, stapler, spy, etc. Hearing the letter "Sh" in the word, the child should wave his hands.

If the child finds it difficult and does not hear the required sound, the presentation should be reflected in the pronunciation.

2. The version of the previous game is already without berlin voice pronunciation.

Place various toys in front of the child and ask them to show the toys containing the letter "Sh" (bear, mouse, baby Masha, ball, etc.).

REFERENCES

1. Curriculum of "Ilk Kadam" preschool educational institution. Tashkent. 2018.
2. Kadirova F. preschool pedagogy. Textbook - Tashkent.
3. www.google.com.